

Lecture 1: Lifting Brauer Characters and Generalized Class Functions

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1. Motivation: From Ordinary to Modular Representation Theory

Let G be a finite group and p a prime dividing $|G|$. While ordinary character theory studies representations over \mathbb{C} , modular representation theory considers representations over a field k of characteristic p . The irreducible characters in this setting are called *Brauer characters*, denoted $\phi \in \text{IBr}(G)$.

2. p -Regular Elements and Domains of Brauer Characters

Definition 1 (p -regular element). *An element $g \in G$ is called p -regular if the order of g is not divisible by p .*

Let:

- $G_{p'}$: the set of p -regular elements of G ,
- $\text{Cl}_{p'}(G)$: the set of p -regular conjugacy classes.

Brauer characters $\phi \in \text{IBr}(G)$ are defined only on $G_{p'}$, and vanish on p -singular elements.

3. Generalized Characters and Class Functions

Let:

- $\mathbb{Z}\text{Irr}(G)$: the group of generalized ordinary characters (i.e., integer linear combinations of $\text{Irr}(G)$),
- $\mathbb{Z}\text{IBr}(G)$: the group of generalized Brauer characters.

Given $\theta \in \mathbb{Z}\text{IBr}(G)$, we aim to lift θ to a class function on all of G , ideally lying in $\mathbb{Z}\text{Irr}(G)$.

4. Two Canonical Lifts of a Brauer Character

Let θ be a class function on $G_{p'}$. We define two lifts:

(1) Tilde Lift (Green's Lift)

Let $|G|_p$ denote the highest power of p dividing $|G|$. Define:

$$\tilde{\theta}(x) = \begin{cases} |G|_p \cdot \theta(x) & \text{if } x \text{ is } p\text{-regular,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

(2) Hat Lift

Let $x = x_p x_{p'}$ be the Jordan decomposition of $x \in G$, where x_p is the p -part and $x_{p'}$ the p' -part. Define:

$$\hat{\theta}(x) = \theta(x_{p'}).$$

5. Lemma (Navarro, Lemma 2.15)

Lemma 1 (Green's Lift Preserves Generalized Characters). *Let $\theta \in \mathbb{Z}\text{Irr}(G)$ or $\theta \in \mathbb{Z}\text{IBr}(G)$. Then both $\tilde{\theta}$ and $\hat{\theta}$ lie in $\mathbb{Z}\text{Irr}(G)$.*

This lemma is proven using a characterization theorem of Brauer (see Navarro, Chapter 2).

6. Brauer's Criterion for Generalized Characters

Theorem 1 (Brauer's Characterization Theorem). *A class function θ on G lies in $\mathbb{Z}\text{Irr}(G)$ if and only if for every p -elementary subgroup $E = P \times Q \leq G$, where P is a p -group and Q is a p' -group, the restriction $\theta|_E \in \mathbb{Z}\text{Irr}(E)$.*

To verify that $\tilde{\theta}, \hat{\theta} \in \mathbb{Z}\text{Irr}(G)$, it suffices to show their restriction to $P \times Q$ lies in $\mathbb{Z}\text{Irr}(P \times Q)$.

7. Example: Regular Character of a p -Group

Example 1. *Let P be a nontrivial p -group. Then $\text{IBr}(P) = \{\phi_{\text{triv}}\}$, and the corresponding projective character is the regular character:*

$$\Phi(x) = \begin{cases} |P| & x = 1, \\ 0 & x \neq 1. \end{cases}$$

This is an example of a lift via $\tilde{\theta}$, concentrated on the identity.

8. Summary

- Brauer characters are defined only on p -regular elements.
- The tilde and hat lifts extend Brauer characters to all of G .
- Lemma 2.15 (Navarro) shows both extensions are generalized characters.
- Brauer's criterion gives a test for when a class function lies in $\mathbb{Z}\text{Irr}(G)$, based on restrictions to p -elementary subgroups.

Next Lecture

In Lecture 2, we will:

- Introduce the decomposition matrix and its entries $d_{\chi\phi}$,
- Define projective indecomposable characters and their duality with $\text{IBr}(G)$,
- Study orthogonality on p -regular classes,
- Examine the inner product matrix and dual basis relationships (see Navarro, Chapter 3).